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Change detection of vegetation cover Using Remote Sensing and GIS

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Abstract — NDVI- a spectral index namely Normalized Difference Vegetation Index is an emerging technique from Remote Sensing and GIS technology to detect spatio-temporal change of vegetation cover for micro regions on the earth surface. The analysis of spatio-temporal change in vegetation cover and its density has a greater significance in taxonomy and understanding overall nature of Biodiversity with response to recent climatic change. This paper analyses the spatio-temporal change and adopted NDVI Taxonomy in a micro region like Tittur basin of Tapi system in northwestern part of Maharashtra state during 1990-2010 based on land-sat imageries of TM and ETM+. (IR and NIR band) of 16 Oct.1990 and 15 Oct. 2010..The NDVI has been worked out for detection of spatio-temporal change in vegetation cover for Tittur basin which ranges between -0.39 to 0.74 and 0. On the basis of NDVI-Taxonomy the Tittur basin can be classified into four categories. The NDVI Value below zero indicates water bodies. The NDVI value above zero is further classified into three groups. Viz. 0.0-0.20 (Bare surface), 0.20- 0.46 (vegetation cover of scrub and stunted brushwood) and 0.46 to 0.74 (dense forest and cropland vegetation) .The temporal variation reveal the -ve change +ve change and no change. The major part of the basin reveal +ve change. All the NDVI Taxonomy groups reveals increasing trend from 1990 to 2010 except bare surface. Titter basin experience considerable decrease of bare surface, which is brought, either in cultivation or under forest. The of density of vegetation also increased .This fact attributed to the increase in rainfall and anthropogenic efforts towards the water conservation.. The rainfall is increased by 100mm during this decade and water reservoirs are increased. This fact certainly proves conservation of biodiversity. Recently, Gavatala National forest is developed and biodiversity is well protected in this region. Tittur basin extents between 20o16'19" - 20o40'7"NL and 74o52'30"- 74o17'33"EL.and covers 972 sq.km area of Tapi basin. It comes under dry deciduous monsoon regime.

Keywords — NDVI, Vegetation cover, Change Detection, GIS, Remote Sensing

1 INTRODUCTION

The Remote Sensing (RS) and emerging GIS technology is the best tool in the hands of researchers of various disciplines of recent generation. The remote sensing provides the spectral data from the satellites without any physical contact to the object in the digital form. This digital data is converted into visual image in the form of imagery. The imagery is the best and reliable source of data of the earth surface in various contexts like topography, biodiversity; land use cultural aspects etc. Geographic Information System (GIS) is very recent technology in the hand of geographer. It is the computer-based system for collecting, storing, checking, integrating, retrieving, manipulating processing, analyzing and displaying data, which are spatially reference to the earth (Burrow 1986). It includes components like computer system, software, spatial data, data managements and analysis procedures to the users. NDVI- a spectral index namely Normalized Difference Vegetation Index is an emerging technique from Remote Sensing and GIS technology to detect spatio-temporal change of vegetation cover for micro regions on the earth surface. The John Rouse. (Dr. John Rouse was the Director of the Remote Sensing Center of Texas A&M University where the Great Plains study was conducted) was the earliest formal reporter of NDVI in 1973. The person responsible for a series of early scientific journal articles describing uses of the NDVI was Compton Tucker of NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center. The, NDVI is one of the most successful of many attempts to simply and quickly identify vegetated areas and their "condition," and it remains the most well-known and used index to detect live green plant canopies in multispectral remote sensing data. NDVI not only detects the vegetation but also demonstrates the quantification of the photosynthetic capacity of forest canopies. The NDVI values always ranges between -1 and +1 because of high reflectance in NIR of EMS. Non-vegetation area has NDVI value less than zero and 0-1 value indicates wide variation of vegetation from bare surface to dense forest canopy. The present paper attempts NDVI taxonomy and detection of spatio-temporal change in vegetation cover of Tittur basin.

2 STUDY AREA

Tittur basin extents between 20°16'19" -20°40'7"NL and 74°52'30"- 74°17'33"EL.and covers 972 sq.km area of Tapi basin. It comes under dry deciduous monsoon regime. Basin is founded on Deccan Trap Formations of Eocene period and experience a wide range of geo-biodiversity.

3 OBJECTIVES

- 3.1 To estimate NDVI from RS data and application of overlay processing.
- 3.2 To prepare NDVI Maps
- 3.3 To identify vegetation cover and its spatial – temporal distribution
- 3.4 To detect the spatio-temporal change.

4 METHODS AND MATERIAL

The aim of this paper is to detect the vegetation change from 1990 to 2010. The multi-spectral satellite data is used to image processing for estimation of NDVI. The software ERDAS-9.2 and ARCGIS-INFO-9.3.1 is used data acquisition and processing. The following flow chart suggests the NDVI image processing and vegetation change detection methods. The data utilized is given in the following tables for the years 1990 and 2010. The NDVI values estimated and classified in a spatial context to prepare NDVI map for both the years. The vegetation change and its density is detected on map. The maps are interpreted by means of interpretative potential to establish casual relationship of vegetation cover and environmental circumstances.

Table 1. Data Source and Acquisition

RS data	Path/Row	Date	Band
Landsat TM	146/46	Oct 1990	1,2,3,4
Landsat TM	146/46	Oct 2010	1,2,3,4

Table 2. Band Combination

Landsat imaginary	Band combination		
	Blue	Green	Red
TrueColour	1	2	3
Fals colour	2	3	4
NDVI	(4-3)/(4+3)		

Fig. 1. NDVI Image processing flow chart

Fig.2. Vegetation Cover Change Detection methodology Flow Chart

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The NDVI Taxonomy maps of Titter basin for both the years reveal four classes of vegetation covers. Viz- water bodies, bare land, scrub & grassland and cropland & dense vegetation. NDVI values for each class of vegetation cover are detected as shown in table 3.

5.1 Spatio-Temporal distribution of Vegetation Cover of Titter basin

The table 3 reflects the NDVI Tittur basin is between -0.74 and +0.74 during 1990-2010. The lower most NDVI value for Tittur basin in 1990 is -0.74. This value is close to the lowest figure of -1 NDVI for no vegetation. The lower value of -0.74 indicates the presence aquatic plants in extremely low proportion. This proportion of aquatic plants increases with increase in water bodies in 2010. The NDVI value above zero to one indicates the terrestrial vegetation with increase in their maximum proportion. The maximum NDVI value for Tittur basin is 0.74 indicates comparative dense vegetation cover. The overall highest value dense vegetation cover is +1. The maximum area of the Tittur basin belongs to the scrub and grasslands. The minimum area lies under water bodies. There was a considerable area of the bare land with extremely low vegetation cover in 1990. The Tittur basin experience considerable spatial and temporal change in vegetation cover. The water bodies becomes nearly doubled from 1990-2010. This fact attributes to the increase in rainfall and adoption of water conservation practices in this area. The average annual rainfall of the basin is increased by nearly 100MM. during 1990-2010. The bare land reveals considerable decrease from 1990 to 2010. The bare land is brought under cropland due to increase of population pressure on land.

5.2 Vegetation Change Detection during 1990 – 2010

Premised on the objective of the present investigation the vegetation area has changed. The spectral signature of cropland and the forest is same. The NDVI is unable to separate cropland from forest area. However, overall change of vegetation may be detected from substring former NDVI map from later. The change detection map is prepared. The overall increased, decreased, and unchanged area is estimated as shown in table 4.

The table 4 reflects the maximum area of increase in vegetation. (64.5%). This increased is probably of cropland. The unchanged area of 32.71 % is of reserved forest. The decreased

area is of the bare surface area.. The density of vegetation cover is detected from the spectral values. The density of vegetation cover is increased dense forest as well as cropland is increased. It is evident from the increased value of NDVI from 0.69 in 1990 to 0.74 in 2010. This fact is attributed to the increase average rainfall, irrigation facilities and protection of forest under development Gaichar National Park.

Table 3. Spatio-Temporal distribution of Vegetation Cover of Titter basin

Vegetation Cover	Year 1990			Year 2010		
	NDVI Values	Area in Sq.Km	Area(%)	NDVI Values	Area in Sq.Km	Area(%)
Water Body	-0.74-0.00	10.59	1.089506	-0.39-0.00	20.05	2.062757
Bare Land	0.00-.20	361.71	37.212963	0.00-.20	130.76	13.452675
Scrub and Grassland	0.20-.46	446.76	45.962963	0.20-.46	547.14	56.290123
Dense Forest cover and Crop land	0.46-.69	152.94	15.734568	0.46-.74	274.05	28.19444
Total	-0.74-0.69	972.00	100	-0.39-0.74	972.00	100

Table 4. Vegetation Change Detection during 1990 - 2010

Vegetation Change Detection	Area (Sq Km)	Area (%)
Increase area	623.54	64.15 %
Decreased area	30.57	3.14 %
Unchanged area	317.89	32.71 %

6 CONCLUSION

NDVI- a spectral index namely Normalized Difference Vegetation Index is an emerging technique from Remote Sensing and GIS technology to detect spatio-temporal change of vegetation cover for micro regions like Tittur Basin of Tapi system in Jalgaon district of Maharashtra.. The vegetation cover of the basin can classify into four NDVI Taxonomic groups. In the present context of climatic change, the average annual rainfall of the basin is increased by nearly 100 mm. The increased rainfall is responsible for spatial, temporal change and increase in density of vegetation cover during 1990-2010.

Fig 3 Location Map of study area

Fig4 NDVI Map of year 1990

Fig 5 NDVI Map of year 2010

Fig 6 Highlight NDVI change detection map

Fig 7 NDVI change Detection Map

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REFERENCES

- 1.HofferR.M.(1978)”Biological and Physical consideration in Applying computer aided analysis technique to remote sensor data. In Remote Sensing : a quantitative approach” edited by P.H. Swam et .el,McGraw-Hill.
- 2.Lillesand T.M.and Keifer W(1994) “Remote Sensing Image Interpretation”, New York: John Wiley.
- 3.MD.Rejaur Raheman et..el (2004) “Change detection of winter crops Coverage and Use of Landsat data with GIS”, The Journal of Geo-Environment Vol.4 PP1-13.
- 4.James B. Campbell (1996, 2002), “Introduction to Remote Sensing”(third edition); the Guilford press, a division of Guilford Publication, Inc 72 spring street New York. NY10012
- 5.Singh .A (1990); ‘Review Article: Digital Change Detection Techniques using Remotely Sensed Data’; International Journal of Remote Sensing; Vol.10 PP 989- 1003
6. Gibbard, S., K. Caldeira, G. Bala, T. J. Phillips, and M. Wickett (2005), Climate effects of global landcover change, Geophys. Res. Lett., 32, L23705, doi:10.1029/2005GL024550.